

Role of Ultrasound B-Scan in Management of Blunt Trauma Injuries in Conjunction with Clinical Findings in a Tertiary Care Eye Centre

Rita Deka¹, Nabajyoti Borah², Arupjyoti Kakati³, Shibashis Deb⁴, Saura Kamal Dutta⁵

^{1,2,5}Dhubri Medical College and Hospital Dhubri

³University of Science and Technology, Meghalaya

⁴Guwahati Medical College and Hospital, Guwahati

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Saura Kamal Dutta

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Abstract:

Background: Globe injuries are a major cause of visual impairment and blindness worldwide. Ocular trauma is frequently associated with facio-maxillary and/or head injuries. The present study was therefore conducted at tertiary care center to study the effectiveness of USG scan in assessing the posterior segment in patients with ocular trauma, so that further treatment plan can be decided and prognosis can be improved.

Methods: The study was conducted at Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, Guwahati during the study period of one year i.e. from 1st July 2022 to 31st June 2023. The data was compiled using Ms Excel and analysed using IBM SPSS software version 20.

Results: A total of 50 patients with history of blunt ophthalmological injury resulting in closed globe injuries and satisfying the inclusion & exclusion criteria were taken up for this study. The socio-demographic data reveals that the age group of 21-30 years (Range-8 to 70 years) were the most commonly affected (28% of all cases) with males having higher incidence than females (70% as compared to 30%). The most common anterior segment morbidity was Subconjunctival Hemorrhage (48%), followed by lid injury (46%). Vitreous hemorrhages (32%) followed by retinal detachment (16%).

Conclusion: USG B-Scan greatly supplements the general clinical approach by detecting, locating, and finding the extent and nature of the lesion.

Keywords: Blunt Trauma, Closed Globe Injury, Ultrasound B Scan.

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Introduction

Globe injuries are a major cause of visual impairment and blindness world-wide. As per WHO report, globally 1.6 million turn blind due to ocular injuries. Blunt trauma constitutes 97% of cases burden [1]. In India, the demographics of ocular injury reports show a prevalence of 2.4% of population out of which blunt trauma constitutes 56% of all ocular injuries [2].

Ocular trauma is frequently associated with facio-maxillary and/or head injuries. 84% of head injuries are complicated by ocular injuries.

The periorbital soft tissue inflammation and injuries, adnexal injuries, sedation, and reduced patient co-operation due to altered sensorium can make globe examination difficult during acute trauma.

Ultrasound is easily accessible, rapid, non-invasive technique which is useful for visualization of deeper soft tissues. In the year 1956, Mundt and Hughes, started the use of ultrasound B-scan in the unidirectional amplitude modulated (A-scan) mode

[3]. Later two-directional cross-sectional brightness (B scan) scan mode was introduced by Baum and Greenwood in 1958 [4]. Both the A-scan and B-scan complement each other and are often used together to outline soft tissue abnormalities; to detect and localize Intra-Ocular Foreign Bodies (IOFB) in case of ocular media opacity. If done by experienced radiologist/ultra-sonographer, B scan gives more than 90% specificity and 90% sensitivity in the diagnosis of ocular injury. It can give better spatial resolution in the evaluation of choroid, retina and vitreous compared to MRI and CT-Scans [5].

The present study was therefore conducted at tertiary care center to study the effectiveness of USG scan in assessing the posterior segment in patients with ocular trauma, so that further management plan can be decided and better prognosis can be expected.

Materials and Methods:

The study was conducted at Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, Guwahati during the study period of one year i.e. from 1st July 2022 to 31st June 2023.

The study was conducted on all the patients with history of blunt ocular trauma irrespective of age, gender, mode of injury, time since injury and visual acuity at the time of presentation. The patients were selected from those who presented either in RIO, GMCH or Dept. of Casualty, GMCH.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients with history of blunt ocular trauma attending RIO, GMCH or Dept. of Casualty, GMCH, Guwahati who had closed globe injuries were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with open-globe injuries, severe ocular injury that warranted destructive surgery, patients with severe poly-trauma, hemodynamically unstable patients and patients refusing to give consent.

Ethical clearance was taken to conduct the study from the Institutional ethical committee. Written consent was obtained from all the patients belonging to more than 18 years of age whereas written consent was obtained from parents/guardians in case of minors.

Patient's name, age, sex, occupation, addresses, and other sociodemographic data was obtained from all the study participants. A detailed medical history of trauma was taken including - mode of injury, time since injury, any relevant history was noted. Detailed systemic and ocular examination was done on all the patients enrolled in the study. Ocular examination included best corrected VA, anterior segment examination, slit lamp biomicroscopy, intra ocular pressure, fundus examination. All the cases were also subjected to B-scan ultrasonography (10 MHz) for ruling out posterior segment pathology.

All the cases were managed based upon ocular examination findings. Other investigations like - OCT, FFA, CT- & MRI - Orbit were done wherever required to aid in diagnosis. All necessary procedures were done at Regional Institute of

Ophthalmology, Guwahati after taking proper consent from the patient. In presence of posterior segment abnormalities such as retinal detachment, retinal tear or avulsion of optic nerve, the patients were referred to higher centre for further management and their diagnosis was corroborated with our USG B-Scan findings.

The B-scan machine used was done using "Biomedix Echovue" with 10 Mhz probe frequency. It is a new generation multipurpose computer-based USG system with both A-scan and B-scan facilities.

USG B-scan was done via contact method – viz. the probe was in contact with the globe via closed eyelids after application of coupling jelly. First, the superior portion was scanned by directing the patients gaze at 12 o' clock. Then the horizontal transverse scan was taken by orienting the probe near the inferior limbus & marker directed nasally. The probe was then shifted downwards towards the lower fornix – thereby progressively examining more anterior aspects of superior orbit. Similar procedure was followed to scan the medial aspect. For axial scans, the patient's eye was fixed in primary gaze and the probe centered over the cornea. Both the orbits were scanned in each case, irrespective of the laterality of the injury.

Statistical Analysis: The data was compiled using Ms Excel and analysed using IBM SPSS software version 20. Data was expressed as frequency and percentage.

Results

A total of 50 patients with history of blunt trauma resulting in closed globe injuries and satisfying the inclusion & exclusion criteria were taken up for this study. The results of the study have been analyzed and the following observations were made. The sociodemographic data reveals that the age group of 21-30 years (Range-8 to 70 years) were the most commonly affected (28% of all cases) with males having higher incidence than females (70% as compared to 30%). Although the right eye had slightly higher preponderance (50% as compared to 44%) it was not of any statistical significance.

Table 1: Distribution of Cases by Age-Group

Age Group (Years)	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
0-10	3	6
11-20	6	12
21-30	14	28
31-40	11	22
41-50	10	20
>50	6	12

Figure 1: Distribution of cases by age group

Table 2: Distribution of Cases by Sex

Sex	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
Male	35	70
Female	15	30

Figure 2: Distribution of cases by sex

At the time of presentation, clinical examination of the patients revealed that majority of the cases (56%) had Visual Acuity of < 6/60 out of which, 8 patients had presenting Visual Acuity of Perception of Light (PL +ve) and 2 patients had No Perception of Light (PL -ve). Out of 50 patients, 24 patients (48%) had media opacity which restricted visualization of internal structures.

Table 3: Visual Acuity at presentation

Visual Acuity	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
6/6 to 6/18	16	32
6/18 to 6/60	6	12
6/60 to FC(+ve) at 1 mt	14	28

HM(+ve)	4	8
PL(+ve)	8	16
PL(-ve)	2	4

Figure 3: Visual acuity on presentation

Examination of the anterior and posterior segment revealed that the most common anterior segment morbidity was Subconjunctival Hemorrhage (48%) followed by Lid injury (46%). The different structures of the anterior segment were affected either alone or in conjunction with posterior segment injuries. The other forms of anterior segment pathology and their percentage have been noted in the table below.

Table 4: Anterior Segment Pathology:

Pathology	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
Lid Injury	23	46
Conjunctival congestion and SCH	24	48
Corneal edema	4	8
Corneal laceration	6	12
Hyphema	16	32
Iridodialysis	5	10
Lens injury (subluxation/dislocation/cataract)	11	22

(*Several cases had multiple pathologies)

Figure 4: Different Anterior segment injuries reported

The most common posterior segment morbidity was Vitreous hemorrhage (32%) followed by Retinal Detachment (16%). The other posterior segment pathologies included - Subhyaloid haemorrhage, Peripheral retinal tear, Choroidal rupture, Choroidal detachment & Posterior Vitreous Detachment.

Table 5: Posterior Segment Pathology

Pathology	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
Vitreous Hemorrhage	16	32
Posterior Vitreous Detachment	6	12
Subhyaloid hemorrhage	3	6
Peripheral retinal tear	4	8
Retinal Detachment	8	16
Choroidal rupture	2	4
Choroidal detachment	1	2

Figure 5: Different Posterior segment injuries reported

B-Scan Findings: Presence of Corneal Edema, Corneal Laceration and Hyphema obscures the direct visualization of anterior segment and in these cases B-scan ultrasonography can reveal Shallow Anterior Chamber, gross Angle Recession, Ciliary Body Detachment and Lens Dislocations. B-scan is

useful in detecting posterior segment abnormalities in presence of hazy media.

In almost half of the cases (48%) there was media opacity due to various causes where direct visualization of the posterior segment was not possible.

Figure 6: Media Clarity

Peripheral Vitreous Detachment is usually smooth and may be thick posteriorly when blood is layered along its surfaces. On the other hand, Vitreous Hemorrhage is easily detected as sonolucent scattered opacities in fresh cases and membrane configuration with Tractional RD in long-standing cases. Retinal Detachment typically appears as a bright, continuous, smooth, and somewhat folded membrane which moves freely in the vitreous on kinetic evaluation. It remains inserted at the optic nerve head. On long standing cases, the movement reduces on kinetic evaluation. The Tractional Retinal Detachment appears as a tented or table top

configuration; the vitreous band connected to anterior surface. Total Retinal Detachment has a triangular funnel shape with the insertions at the ora serrata and the optic nerve head.

In comparison, Choroidal thickening appears in a spongy pattern whereas Choroidal Detachment appears as dome-shaped opacity with little after-movement on kinetic evaluation, which is limited anteriorly to the ciliary body and posteriorly to exit foramina of vortex veins.

The incidence of various abnormalities detected by B-scan is tabulated in

Table 6: Different USG B-Scan findings in blunt ocular trauma

B-Scan Findings	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Hyphema alone	11	22
Hyphema + cataract/subluxation	4	8
Hyphema + cataract/subluxation + vitreous haemorrhage + retinal detachment	1	2
Subluxation of lens + vitreous haemorrhage	3	6
Dislocation/Subluxation of lens	3	6
Vitreous haemorrhage + posterior vitreous detachment	6	12
Vitreous haemorrhage + Retinal detachment	6	12
Subhyaloid haemorrhage	3	6
Retinal detachment alone	1	2
Peripheral retinal tear/dialysis	4	8
Choroidal Detachment	1	2
Choroidal Rupture	2	4

Discussion

Ocular trauma results in significant morbidity responsible for serious handicap leading to personal as well as national socio-economic burden. At times, detection of posterior segment pathology becomes difficult clinically when the cornea, lens and the media become opaque due to the injury. In such cases, the diagnosis relies largely on radiological investigations like ultrasound B-scan and CT scan.

The incidence of ocular trauma varies with age, the highest being in the 3rd decade. Doshi (1968) [6], Olurin (1979) [7] and Ilsar et al (1982) [8] found that the highest incidence of ocular trauma in third decade of life with an incidence of 21%, 32% and 35% respectively. In our study also the highest incidence was in the 3rd decade (28%). In the present study, incidence of ocular trauma had higher male preponderance (70%). This may be due to relatively higher exposure to outdoor activities and occupational injuries, which corroborates with other studies. Conjunctival congestion and subconjunctival hemorrhage were the most common anterior segment injuries (48%), followed by lid injuries (46%). Hyphema was found in 32% cases while corneal laceration in 12% cases and iridodialysis in 10% cases. Lens injury including dislocation and traumatic cataract was found in 22% cases. Arushi Kakkar et al (2022) reported the incidence of lid edema and lid ecchymosis in

62.6% and 61.8% cases respectively [9], followed by subconjunctival hemorrhage in 60.6% cases. The study by Raju KV et al [10] reported that 34.55% patients had corneal abrasions and 54.55% had Hyphema and traumatic cataract was 12.73%. A study by Henry showed the incidence of traumatic cataract as 11% [11], while the study by Britten reported it to be 15% [12].

In our study, the most common posterior segment manifestation was vitreous hemorrhage (32%), followed by retinal detachment (16%). Posterior vitreous detachment was seen in 12% patients, Peripheral retinal tear in 8%, choroidal injury in 6% and subhyaloid hemorrhage in 6% each. The study by Henry [11] noted incidence of vitreous hemorrhage in 10% cases & chorioretinal injuries was 14%, while Britten [12] noted incidence of vitreous hemorrhage to be 15% and chorioretinal injuries to be 18%.

The study by Raju KV [10] et al reported 21.82% incidence of vitreous hemorrhage, while 3.64% had retinal detachment and 9.09% had choroidal tear. Krishnan and Sreenivasan (1988) [11] reported incidence of vitreous hemorrhage to be 20.7%. In the present study, with the help of B-scan Ultrasonography, 32 cases of vitreous hemorrhage, 16 cases of retinal detachment and 12 cases of posterior vitreous detachment, corresponding with the clinical findings. Thus, the sensitivity of B-scan was 100% in diagnosing these manifestations of

blunt ocular trauma. In a study by Atta HR, a total of 66 cases of vitreous hemorrhage were clinically diagnosed, which correlates with B-scan findings [14]. Thus, B-scan ultrasonography is an accurate method of diagnosing vitreous hemorrhage. Taraprasad Das and P. Namperumalsamy (1987) analyzed and described 175 recent and old traumatized eyes in the presence of opaque ocular media. Out of them Ultrasonography detected 34 cases of vitreous haemorrhage, 33 cases of cataract, 12 cases of intraocular foreign body and 22 cases of retinal detachment [15]. B-scan USG is a non-invasive, safe and easily repeatable procedure which can identify both the exact dimension of the globe and the nature of the lesion.

Conclusion

Ocular trauma is important cause of morbidity and visual loss in children to middle aged males, which can be prevented by adopting safety measures especially in children and occupational individuals. Clinical examination along with routine investigations like X-rays may not be adequate in cases of closed globe injuries with extensive anterior chamber involvement where direct visualization of posterior segment is not possible. Morbidity and visual loss caused by closed globe injuries can be prevented by doing USG B-Scan along with clinical correlation, because:

1. Early Surgical intervention can be planned based on the findings of USG B-Scan.
2. Referral to higher centre, if necessary, can be done after diagnosis of posterior segment pathology, especially in hazy media.

This rapid and non-invasive diagnostic tool has been found to be sensitive and accurate in diagnosis of the different manifestations of blunt ocular trauma. USG B-Scan greatly supplements the general clinical approach by detecting, locating, and finding the extent and nature of the lesion and helps planning proper management.

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